

Study on Spacer Fabrics Used for Uppers of Athletic Shoes

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Abstract:

Recent advancements in sports shoe fabrics have significantly enhanced both functionality and comfort. This article delves into the evolving landscape of active sports shoe fabrics, particularly emphasizing the application of advanced textile materials in athletic shoes. Integrating advanced textile science in sports shoe manufacturing is crucial to meet the varied demands of different athletic activities. Selecting the right materials is essential to ensure optimal comfort, flexibility, breathability, strength, fit, and overall performance. The paper highlights the importance of fabric materials and construction methods, especially for the upper parts of sports shoes. The comfort and performance of fabrics used in shoe uppers made from spacer fabrics have been evaluated and compared.

Keywords: Athletic shoe, Comfort, Polyamide, Polyester, Spacer Fabrics, Technical textiles

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1. Introduction

The prevalence of sports shoes extends beyond professional athletes to include fitness enthusiasts and individuals partaking in outdoor activities for leisure and well-being. This wider demand for sports shoes with tailored fabric properties has spurred advancements in materials to meet consumer expectations.

The importance of the shoe's upper materials is underscored, emphasizing their influence on stability, comfort, and athlete performance. Nylon mesh, renowned for its breathability, lightweight nature, and quick-drying properties, plays a pivotal role in facilitating air circulation and minimizing moisture accumulation within the shoe [1].

Traditional materials like Polyamide, Polyester, Nylon, PU, and PVC, while durable, often fell short in terms of breathability, comfort, and lightweight design. New materials utilized in sports shoe orthotics, encompassing both the uppers and insoles, showcase superior properties when juxtaposed with traditional materials. Knitted materials, nylon, Lycra, smart fabrics, and PU insoles are instrumental in fostering breathability, lightweight design, and proficient moisture control, thereby elevating overall comfort and performance. [1, [2]. Insoles made from modern materials like PU, knitted mesh, and smart textiles further enhance foot support, stability, and overall comfort during sporting activities [3, 4].

Spacer fabrics have emerged as a revolutionary alternative, offering the requisite strength, breathability, and traction essential for sports shoe construction. The expanding market for sports shoes, propelled by health-conscious consumers participating in diverse outdoor activities, has prompted research into functional fabrics [5]. Producers are concentrating on improving the performance and durability of sports shoes to meet the growing demand [6], [7].

Spacer fabrics are uniquely defined by their open 3D structure as shown in Fig.1, which enhances airflow, moisture-wicking, and heat dissipation during physical activity. Additionally, the inherent shock-absorbing properties of these textiles significantly reduce joint stress during high-impact exercises. Their notable advantages encompass efficient moisture management, breathability, cushioning, shock absorption, pressure dispersion, durability, and minimizing bacterial growth [8, 9]. These attributes enhance athlete performance, comfort, and overall satisfaction. Furthermore, the material's durability and resistance to wear ensure long-lasting performance [5, 10]. The use of

spacer fabrics in sports shoe orthotics offers numerous benefits to both athletes and manufacturers [1]. Knitted mesh materials offer improved liquid transport capabilities, flexibility, and breathability, contributing to comfortable foot movement and reduced friction [11, 12].

The production of spacer fabrics involves specialized knitting or weaving techniques, incorporating warp and weft yarns and spacer yarns to create a resilient three-dimensional textile. Finishing processes, such as heat setting or bonding, enhance the stability and durability of spacer fabrics [13, 14].

Figure 1 - Structure of spacer fabric [10]

Spacer fabric characteristics, in contrast to conventional materials, spacer textiles have several distinctive qualities that make them ideal for sports shoe orthotics [15].

In this study, five different types of shoe upper materials were investigated and the effect of material composition and structural characteristics on comfort and performance characteristics were evaluated. The findings contribute to a deeper understanding of the material characteristics crucial for shoe orthotics.

2. Methodology

2.1 Material

This study investigates the properties of five spacer fabrics (coded as S1, S2, S3, S4, and S5) shown in Fig. 2 provided by three international athletic shoe manufacturers. The fabrics were disintegrated, and the layer-wise fibre composition is evaluated as per standard ASTM D629. The results are shown in table 1.

Figure 2 - Spacer fabric samples

Table 1 - Fiber composition of spacer fabric samples

Sample Code		S1	S2	S3	S4	S5
Layer 1	Composition	100 % Polyester	100 % Polyester	100 % Polyester	100 % Polyester	98 % Polyester +2% Elastane
Layer 2	Composition	100 % Polyester	100 % Polyester	100 % Polyester	100 % Polyester	98 % Polyester +2% Elastane
Layer 3	Composition	100 % Polyester	100 % Polyester	100 % Polyester	100 % Polyester	100 % Polyester

The fabric properties like fabric weight, fabric thickness, water vapor permeability, tear strength, extension are evaluated as per standards given in Table 2.

**Table 2: Standard test methods and minimum requirements of fabrics for shoe upper
Material: Spacer Fabrics used in construction of shoe orthotics (Upper) [16]**

Sr. No.	Test Name	Test Method	Requirement
1	Thickness of Fabrics	GE 05	1-3 (mm)
2	Spacer Fabric Weight	GE 07	200-400(GSM)
3	Spacer Fabric Tear Strength A	ST 02	0.03 kN (min)
4	Spacer Fabric Tear Strength B	ST 02	0.03 kN (min)
5	Spacer Fabric Tensile Strength A	ST 03	0.600 kN/0.05m (min)
6	Spacer Fabric Tensile Strength B	ST 03	0.400 kN/0.05m (min)
7	Spacer Fabric Elongation A	ST 03	40 percent (min)
8	Spacer Fabric Elongation B	ST 03	60 percent (min)
9	Spacer Fabric Water Vapour Permeability	IS 15298 (part 2) 2016	0.0008 g/cm ² h
10	Spacer Fabric Water Vapour Coefficient	IS 15298 (part 2) 2016	0.150 g/cm ²

Fabric weight and thickness are fundamental parameters for testing different groups of fabrics. Standardized results are crucial, considering the direct relationships between weight, stiffness, and heat with thickness. The study adheres to standardized testing methods, including specimen dimensions, mass/area considerations, and controlled environments for precision in results.

Tensile and tear strengths are vital in athletic shoes, influencing breaking and elongation properties. Tensile Strength, dependent on axial stretching load, is determined by fabric structure and fiber composition. Tear strength evaluates the fabric's ability to withstand tearing along a line, especially relevant in non-leather athletic shoe components. The clamping arrangement is shown in Figure 3

Figure 3 - The clamping arrangement of fabrics on tear tester

The standards used for the weight test include [3] Extension, represented by the ratio of stretching to actual length, is crucial in assessing fabric stability. Young's modulus measures the stretch due to small stress, with soft materials exhibiting lower modulus compared to stiffer fabrics.

Abrasion resistance is critical in evaluating fabric performance and longevity. The study explores different types of machines, methods, and testing environments to assess the impact of abrasion on fabric structure and properties.

Water vapor permeability is a critical aspect of safety footwear because it directly impacts the comfort and health of the wearer. Proper water vapor permeability allows sweat to escape from the inside of the shoe, maintaining a dry and comfortable environment for the feet, which is particularly important in demanding work environments.

The testing method typically involves measuring the amount of water vapor that passes through the material over a specific period. The result is usually expressed in grams per square centimetres per hour ((g/cm²h)). Along with permeability, the standard may also require measurement of the water vapor coefficient, which is the ratio of the amount of water vapor passing through the material to the area and time. This coefficient helps in understanding how efficiently the footwear manages moisture.

3. Results and Discussions

The performance and comfort characteristics of fabrics are shown in Table 3. It could be observed that all the samples are of similar fabric weight per unit and are of same fiber composition apart from sample S5.

Table 3 - Performance and comfort characteristics of fabrics for shoe upper

S. No.	Fabric characteristics	Test Method	Sample No.				
			S1	S2	S3	S4	S5
01	Thickness of Fabrics (mm)	GE 05	2.54	2.82	2.52	2.85	3.00
02	Fabric Weight (g/m ²)	GE 07	274	284	272	285	282
03	Tear Strength (N) lengthwise	ST 02	84.3	82.3	80.2	84.6	82.8
04	Tear Strength (N) cross grain	ST 02	69.3	68.3	67.3	69.6	68.2
05	Tensile Strength (N) Lengthwise	ST 03	1105	1102	1100	1108	1104
06	Tensile Strength (N) cross grain	ST 03	418	420	412	421	423
07	Elongation % Lengthwise	ST 03	61	64	62	6	74
08	Elongation % cross grain	ST 03	85	83	82	84	93
09	Spacer Fabric Water Vapour Permeability (g/cm ² h)	IS 15298, Part 2: 2016	0.0755	0.0782	0.0759	0.0842	0.0891
10	Spacer Fabric Water Vapour Coefficient (g/cm ²)	IS 15298, part 2: 2016	0.5615	0.7437	0.5276	0.8474	0.9843

The thickness of these fabrics ranges from 2.5mm to 3mm. The effect of thickness on performance and comfort properties is evaluated using the statistical method ANOVA. As observed in Table 4, the p-value for all correlations is found to be less than 0.05. So, it could be interpreted that the thickness of the spacer fabric has a significant effect on the performance properties and comfort characteristics of spacer fabrics.

The effect of thickness on the durability of knit fabrics can vary depending on several factors. In this study, It has been observed that tear strength as well as tensile strength increases with an increase in thickness. Thicker fabrics typically have more material per unit area, which can provide greater resistance to tearing. Thicker knit fabrics may offer better structural integrity, with more yarns interlocking or entangling within the fabric structure. This can enhance tear resistance by distributing stress more evenly across the fabric. Thicker knit fabrics may have higher yarn density, with more yarns interlocking within the fabric structure. This dense arrangement of yarns can enhance the load-bearing capacity of the fabric and contribute to higher tensile strength.

Table 4: One-way ANOVA of Spacer Fabrics' physical characteristics

Fabric physical properties	R ² Value of Spacer fabric	P-value of Spacer Fabrics
Relationship between Spacer's Fabric Tear Strength and Thickness	0.084	0.009
The correlation between a Spacer fabric's thickness and tensile strength	0.771	0.001
The correlation between a Spacer fabric's thickness and weight	0.764	0.002
The correlation between water Vapour Permeability and Thickness of Spacer Fabrics	0.830	0.035

As noted in Table 3, the moisture vapor permeability of the fabric increased as its thickness increased. Typically, thicker fabrics tend to be heavier and impede the movement of moisture vapor. However, contrary to this expectation, our study observed an opposite trend. This could be attributed to the fact that all fabric samples had the same weight,

meaning that thicker fabrics had lower density and thus more porosity. Increased porosity results in more open spaces, allowing moisture to pass through more easily, thereby enhancing the fabric's transmittance characteristics.

Sample S5 has 2 % elastane in its composition which explains the higher extensibility of this fabric as compared to other. Extension in sports shoe uppers ensures a secure and adaptive fit, accommodating foot movements during dynamic activities. It enhances comfort, prevents slippage, and reduces the risk of injuries. The optimal extension supports agility and performance, crucial for athletes across various sports disciplines. Hence incorporation of elastane could enhance the agility and comfort of athletic shoes.

The fabric samples were evaluated across various properties using a scale of 1 to 5, as depicted in Figure 3. Sample 5, despite being thicker yet lighter and containing elastane, demonstrated superior performance and comfort compared to others.

Figure 4 - Various properties of samples using a scale of 1 to 5

Table 5 - Various properties of samples using a scale of 1 to 5

			S1	S2	S3	S4	S5
1	Fabric's Thickness	GE 05	4	3	5	2	1
2	Fabric's Weight	GE 07	4	2	5	1	3
3	Fabric's Tensile Strength	ST 03	4	3	5	2	1
4	Fabric's Elongation	ST 03	5	3	4	2	1
5.	Fabric moisture vapour permeability	IS 15298, part 2: 2016	4	3	5	2	1

4. Conclusion

The in-depth analysis provides insights into fabric composition, 3D structures, thickness, weight, and mechanical properties of spacer fabrics used in athletic shoe orthotics. This work examined the permeability and conductivity characteristics of polyester filament-based warp-knitted spacer textiles. When applying shoe orthotics, the spacer fabric is thought to produce a cozy material that normalizes heat transfer during physical activities. The study establishes significant relationships between fabric thickness and various properties. These relationships, analyzed through P-values and regression, reveal correlations between thicknesses and tear strength, tensile strength, weight, and water vapor permeability. The findings showed that the permeability of water vapor and air is dependent on the thickness of the spacer fabrics. The essential component of spacer fabrics' permeability and conductivity are their structure and material composition.

This study contributes valuable knowledge for the selection of materials in the construction of sports shoe orthotics, guiding manufacturers towards optimal fabric choices for enhanced athletic performance and comfort.

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